

A HYPER-HEURISTIC METHOD FOR SCHEDULING THE JOBS IN CLOUD ENVIRONMENT

Deepa.K^{1*}, Prabhu.S², Dr.N.Sengottaiyan³

^{*1}M.E.Scholar, ²Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Nandha Engineering College, Erode, Tamil Nadu, India.

³Vice Principal, Hindustan College of Engineering and Technology, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

ABSTRACT

Currently cloud computing has turned into a promising technology and has become a great key for satisfying a flexible service oriented, online provision and storage of computing resources and user's information in lesser expense with dynamism framework on pay per use basis. In this technology Job Scheduling Problem is a critical issue. For well-organized managing and handling resources, administrations, scheduling plays a vital role. This paper shares out the improved Hyper-Heuristic Scheduling Approach to schedule resources, by taking account of computation time and makespan with two detection operators. Operators are used to select the low-level heuristics automatically. Conditional Revealing Algorithm (CRA) idea is applied for finding the job failures while allocating the resources. We believe that proposed hyper-heuristic achieve better results than other individual heuristics.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing, Job Scheduling Problem, Hyper-Heuristic Scheduling Algorithm, Makespan Time, job failure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerous available measures have been expected to improve, to get better the execution of information systems; in general with respect to computation, limit and examinations. Since parallel and in addition distributed computing was widely used to update the execution of a collection of information systems for different methodologies and heritable limitations in typical ages. The approach to manage these computer resources effectively, despite of which concern it is for is the rule issue. Among them, the most critical one for the booming process of computer system is scheduling. In a given time period the allotment of different jobs to specified resources is called Scheduling. In the cloud environment, it is one of the most prominent actions that execute to increase the efficiency of the workload to get maximum profit.

Recently, the new impel prototype has been efficiently utilized for data frameworks and computer systems i.e. Cloud computing. Organizations today are taking cloud computing as more expert and intelligible way for building their data in advance stages. Cloud computing environment brings self-register, self-administration, client relationship administration, self-administration inventory, organizing and vast information examination. It is actually with reference to hardware and software facility delivered virtually to any device.

Cloud approach is the union of three major abstractions;

- Virtualization
- Utility Computing and
- Software-as-a-Service based on pay-per-usebasis, which is the feature of today's computing.

It is the collection of administrations, applications, framework which are present in datacenter. A hugepart of the Traditional scheduling algorithms are ordinary –based scheduling algorithms usually used on today's appropriated systems. These algorithms are simple and easy to accomplish; sincethe issue in handling the widelevel or difficult scheduling issues these algorithms are inappropriate in acquiring the perfect results.

Heuristics plays a vital role in scheduling on cloud computing Systems. To solve scheduling issue and reasons of erudition and invention, heuristics hints to several practice based frameworks in discovering a solution which is sufficient for the given collection of objectives apart from but it is not definite to be perfect/best. The most vitalpurpose of Hyper-Heuristic is to decideprecise algorithms for a definite issue on the basis of collection of existing algorithms and their execution to variousdegrees. The essential deal of the proposed algorithm is to hold the value/quality of low-level heuristic algorithms like Particle swarm Optimization (PSO) and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) by coordinating them into single algorithm. To improve the performance of Hyper-Heuristic approach, various techniques such as Conditional Revealing algorithm isapplied to look up the overall performance of the system by reducing the makespan time.

The remaining paper is coordinated as follows. Section II begins with a brief introduction of Job Scheduling problem and Hyper-Heuristic. In Section III Related Work is examined. In Section IV, The Proposed work has been discussed. Finally, Section VI draws the conclusion notes together with some understandings about the future research.

2. SCHEDULING IN CLOUD

In Cloud Computing, Scheduling assumes anessential part in effectively dealing with the computer administrations; it is the progress of enchanting choices in regards to the distribution of accessible limit and/or resources to jobs and/or clients within the time. Million of clients put forward cloud administrations by presenting their huge number of processing tasks to the cloud computing environment. Scheduling of these enormous amounts of tasks is a clash to the cloud environment. The scheduling catastrophe in cloud makes it tough to work out, imperiously on account of extensivecomplex jobs like workflows, in order to solve these types of big problems many algorithms are proposed. Scheduling is the method of partitioning tasks to available resources on the assertion of task's traits and requirement. The primary objective of scheduling is prolonged use of the resources without influencing the administrations provided by cloud. Scheduling technique in cloud is segregated into three stages to be specific;

- **Resource verdict and sifting:** In Resource verdict and sifting the datacenter expert finds the advantages present in the framework structure and assembles status data regarding to the benefits.

- **Resource determination:** In Resource determination the objective resource is selected in context of the necessities of assignments and resources. This is a selection stage.
- **Task section:** In jobpackage, the task is dispersed to choose resource.

The clients will only need to represent the task and point out the details with that of their provisions. Everything else is handled by the envoy i.e. broker of the cloud provider. The task is assigned to the resources of the virtual machine and executed.

Fig 1: Scheduling Process on Cloud

3. JOB SCHEDULING PROBLEM

JSP is an optimization concern in which ultimate jobs are owed to resources at definite times in software engineering and operation research. The major answer for problem is that for example n jobs must be transformed on m machines, chooses the case of landing of jobs i.e., queue on every one machine in order to complete all the jobs on all the machines. Here each machine acquires different timings to complete the requested jobs without any priorities. [5] The problem is to find the best job groupings, setup times on the machines in minimum time by using the ACO computation. A job shop ordinarily comprises of large number of general purpose machines, as opposed to several purpose machines which would typically happen in an assembly line. Every job relying on its technological fundamentals, requests handling on machines are done in an order. The JSP should be an extremely puzzling issue. Numerically, the greatest no. of possible progressions with n jobs and m machines is $(n!)^m$ i.e. greatly considerable. The issue is ordinarily explained by close estimation or heuristic procedures. The prerequisite for job scheduling in

cloud focuses on a couple of parameters, for instance, load equality, throughput, Quality of Service (QoS), running time, adequacy, cost, space and so forth. Besides, upgrade the class of entire distributed computing environment.

3.1. Need of scheduling

In Cloud, the job scheduling objectives is to provide ideal task scheduling to clients, and afford the entire cloud framework QoS and throughput in the meantime. The needs of job scheduling in cloud computing are as follows:

- **Load Balance** - In the cloud environment, Load Balancing and task scheduling has determinedly associated with one another. Task scheduling system is in charge for the perfect coordinating of tasks and resources. Task scheduling algorithm can uphold load balancing. Thus load balancing get to be another essential measure in the cloud.
- **Quality of Service** - The cloud is mainly to deliver clients with processing and cloud storage administrations, resource interest for clients and resources supplied by supplier to the clients in such a way so that , quality of service can be accomplished. When job scheduling management comes to job portion, it is significant to make sure about QoS of resources.
- **Best running time** - Jobs can be partitioned into various classes as per the requests of clients, and after that locate the best running time on the basis of distinctive objectives for every task. It will improve the QoS of task scheduling ultimately in a cloud infrastructure.
- **Economic Principles** - Cloud computing resources are largely appropriated all the way through the world. These resources may belong to distinguishing links. Each association/links have their own particular administration approaches. As a business representation, cloud computing as indicated by the distinct provisions, give major administrations. So the significance charges are realistic.

4. HYPER-HEURISTICS

Heuristics are the trouble solving method which can be utilized to patch up the testing and non-routine issues. The main three key operations are Transition, Evaluation and Determination (TED) of heuristics has been utilized to search for the feasible solutions on the convergence system.

- Transition (T) makes the collection (s) s is the solution space, by utilizing routines which could be either perturbative or productive or both.
- Evaluation (E): measures the appropriateness of (s), by making use of predefined estimation.
- Determination (D): decides the subsequent search directions based on (s) from the transition operation and evaluation operation.

The comprehensive revision of heuristic join together two or all the more high –performance scheduling algorithms which can give a superior scheduling in a logical time i.e. Hyper-heuristics. It is intended to expertise their heuristic evaluation process. Hyper-heuristics aims to

find out some algorithms that are ready for solving an entire scale of issues, with slight or non-coordinate human control. There may be an immeasurable number of heuristics from which one can make a decision for solving an issue, and each heuristic has its own precise points of interest and inconveniences. The thought is to accordingly formulate algorithms by strengthen the quality and modifying for the shortcomings of identified heuristics. A usual framework incorporates a high level methodology and numerous low level heuristics [2]. At the point when an problem is given, the high level approach picks which low level heuristic must to be applied and this depends on the search space of the issue and the present issue state. The issues are solved by finding a solution from the array of every possible solution for a given concern, which is viewed as the "search space". The learning point have to refine the algorithms, so that the algorithm solutions consequently deal with the needs of the training set and issues of a certain class can be clarified more profitably. The reaction mechanism should move towards ideal algorithm solutions in the workspace, as it helps the determination of heuristic. Hyper Heuristic is the organization of two or more heuristic algorithms and expects to tell what measures of meta-heuristics are used to solve the current problem. Moreover it can be used to characterize the appropriate meta-heuristic for the given problem. The key idea of Hyper-heuristic is to use "unique" heuristic algorithm at each iteration, with a specific finishing target to keep up high search multiplicity to build the opportunity of finding better solutions at later cycles at the same time as not increasing the makespan.

5. PRIOR WORK

Various authors have figured over the JSP and have been seen as N-P hard problem.. With the procedure of Heuristic approach, a couple of frameworks were anticipated by authors to handle this scheduling problem and among those schedules that have accomplished best results are: In 1985, Davis proposed Job Shop Problem with the use of Genetic Algorithm. There are various works nearby the use of advancement procedures. In 2014, C.W.Tsai[1] proposed a novel Hyper-Heuristic Scheduling Algorithm to comprehend JSP to decrease makespan time and to discover better scheduling solutions for cloud computing frameworks. Two detection operators have been utilized by the proposed algorithm to adjust the intensification and expansion in the hunt of solutions during the convergence procedure. Shortest Processing Time (SPT) cross breed heuristic methodology has been proposed by Zhon and Feng for dealing with scheduling issue. Feasible pheromone adjustment system for advancement of fundamental ant structure which offers in examination of the arrangement space is proposed by Zhang.J[2]. Total Make span time of set of jobs is minimizing by applying heuristic method [27] of SPT (Shortest Processing Time) and methodology of LMC (Largest Marginal Contribution) by Aftab.M.T. In 2012, [26] S.B.Zhan has proposed an examination concerning the usage of Improved Particle Swarm Optimization combined with Simulated Annealing Algorithm in resource scheduling procedure of cloud computing to streamline the JSP, by expanding the convergence speed and use proportion of resources. In 2013, R.G.Babukarthik [29] have proposed a Hybrid Algorithm build on Ant Colony Optimization and Cuckoo Search to advance JSP.B.T.Bini[30] has proposed Hyper-Heuristic Scheduling on Cloud based frameworks. Genetic and Simulated Annealing Algorithms are utilized as a part of the candidate pool as low-level heuristic algorithms. In further the Differential evolution consolidated with the Genetic algorithm to expand the execution, maximum Lateness, maximum tardiness, makespan and maximum stream time are the execution measurements, utilized to make examinations.

6. THE PROPOSED WORK

In cloud computing systems to indenture the makespan time of jobs, a high level performance “Improved Hyper-Heuristic Scheduling Algorithm (IHHSa)” is proposed. This Algorithm combines two low-level scheduling algorithms i.e. ACO and PSO to kick off best scheduling solutions with low calculation time. From the puddle/pool of candidate one algorithm is picking as heuristic algorithm. Two operators are used i.e. diversity detection operator that automatically build out which algorithm is picked and perturbation operator to optimize the results produced by each of these algorithms to further boost makespan time. The key idea of Hyper-heuristic is to use "unique" heuristic algorithm at each iteration, with a specific finishing target to keep up high search multiplicity to build the opportunity of finding better solutions at later cycles at the same time as not increasing the makespan. For the additional enhancement in the performance of HHSa approach, in terms of lower makespan time, conditional revealing operator is used to find the job failures.

6.1. The Intensification Operator

Intensification operator is used to pick up the low-level heuristics H_i from the search space/candidate pool. For that simple random method is used to pick up the heuristics. In line with observation, the BSFMK (best so far completion time i.e., makespan for both Simulated Annealing and Genetic Algorithm could continue to get better results at early iterations (e.g., below 200 iterations), but it is hard to improve the results at afterward iterations (e.g., later 800 iterations), particularly when the search directions come together to a small number of directions. Here we are using ACO and PSO algorithms to find the BSFMK based on iterations. If the selected H_i cannot progress the BSFMK after a row of later iterations, the intensification operator will return a fake value to the high level agitated centre to point out that it should pick up a new LLH. The intensification operator will return a fake value in three situations:

- When the maximum number of iterations is reached,
- When the solutions are not better, and
- When the stop state is reached.

6.2. The Diversity Revealing Operator

Further the intensification operator, the diversity revealing operator is used by IHHSa to make a decision “when” to vary the low-level heuristic algorithm H_i . Here the first solution is used as a threshold value. Then the range of the current solution is computed and it can be taken as the average of the jobs. If the range of the current solution is less than the threshold value the operator returns false value and then it automatically goes to select a new LLH (low-level heuristics).

6.3. Conditional Revealing Operator

Condition revealing operator is to establish the selection of server for scheduling the task with various parameters and timings to take up the low-level heuristic algorithm. By using this operator, the job failures can be easily identified and can analyse the cause of failure. It calculates the number of failure jobs from the earlier service. Job failure can be predict by the type of job, time dependency, factor involved with job failures. Unsuitability prediction can also be checked

to avoid delays. Job state ex: active/finished/paused and acknowledgement are factors considered to check frequently.

6.4. Algorithm for Improved HNSA procedure

- 1) The parameter set up over search space.
- 2) Give input to the job scheduling problem.
- 3) The population of solutions $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ can be Initialize.
- 4) Select a heuristic algorithm H_i based on the Iterations from the candidate pool H .
- 5) If termination criteria is met
- 6) {
- 7) End;
- 8) }
- 9) else
- 10) {
- 11) continue;
- 12) }
- 13) Update the population of solutions X , and feedback F by using the selected algorithm H_i .
- 14) $F_1 =$ Intensification operator(X).
- 15) $F_2 =$ Diversity operator(X)
- 16) $F_3 =$ Conditional operator(X)
- 17) If $\psi(H_i, F_1, F_2, F_3)$
- 18) filter and select H_i based on the F .
- 19) Output the best so far solution as the final solution.
- 20) end

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper an efficient fine-tuned high-level heuristic for a job scheduling problem to reduce the comprehensive make span time of given collection is displayed. The projected algorithm uses three revealing operators. The intensification and diversity operators is proposed on longing to make out when to variant the low-level heuristic algorithm and a conditional revealing operator to shine up the outcome gained by each low-level algorithm to enhance the scheduling possessions in terms of makespan. The Improved Hyper Heuristics provides enhanced results than the usual rule-based algorithms and also other heuristic algorithms in cloud computing environments. The simple suggestion of the projected "improved hyper-heuristic" algorithm is to influence the possessions of all the low-level algorithms. The major part is that to identify with the form of job/task failures with the purpose of civilizing the reliability of the necessary cloud infrastructure from the viewpoint of cloud providers.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chun-Wei Tsai, Wei-Cheng Huang, Meng-Hsiu Chiang, Ming-Chao Chiang and ChuSing Yang, "A Hyper-Heuristic Scheduling Algorithm for Cloud", IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing, January 2014.
- [2] J.Zhang, X.Hu, X.Tan, J.H.Zhong, and Q.Huang, "Implementation of an Ant Colony Optimization Technique for Job Scheduling Problem", Transc. Of the Institute of Measurement and Control, (2006), pp. 93-108.

- [3] M. Rahman, X. Li and H. Palit, "Hybrid heuristic for scheduling data analytics workflow applications in hybrid cloud environment," Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Parallel and Distributed Processing Workshops, 2011.
- [4] C. W. Tsai and J. Rodrigues, "Metaheuristic scheduling for cloud: A survey", IEEE Systems Journal , vol. 8, no. 1, 2014.
- [5] Y.Fang,F.Wang and J.Ge," A Task Scheduling Algorithm Based on Load Balancing in Cloud Computing," Springer–Verlag Berlin Heidelberg,(2010),pp.271-277.
- [6] Wanqing You, Kai Qian, and Ying Qian, "Hierarchical Queue-Based Task Scheduling", Journal of Advances in Computer Networks, Vol. 2, No. 2, 2014.
- [7] Jing Liu, Xing-GuoLuo, Xing-Ming Zhang, Fan Zhang and Bai-Nan Li, "Job Scheduling Model for Cloud Computing Based on Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm", International Journal of Computer Science Issues, Vol. 10, Issue 1, No 3, January 2013.
- [8] Luiz F. Bittencourt, Edmundo R. M. Madeira, and Nelson L. S. da Fonseca, University of Campinas, "Scheduling in Hybrid Clouds," IEEE Communications Magazine, 0163-6804/12, September 2013.
- [9] Jia Zhao, Kun Yang, Xiaohui Wei, Yan Ding, Liang Hu and GaochaoXu, "A Heuristic Clustering-based Task Deployment Approach for Load Balancing Using Bayes Theorem in Cloud Environment", IEEE Transactions On Parallel And Distributed Systems, June 2014.
- [10] Fan Zhang, Junwei Cao, Kai Hwang, Keqin Li and Samee U. Khan, "Adaptive Workflow Scheduling on Cloud Computing Platforms with Iterative Ordinal Optimization", IEEE Transactions On Cloud Computing, Vol. 3, No. 2, April/June 2015.
- [11] Yang Wang and Wei Shi, " Budget-Driven Scheduling Algorithms for Batches of MapReduce Jobs in Heterogeneous Clouds", IEEE Transactions On Cloud Computing, Vol. 2, No. 3, July-September 2014.
- [12] Jing Liu, Xing-GuoLuo, Xing-Ming Zhang, Fan Zhang and Bai-Nan Li, "Job Scheduling Model for Cloud Computing Based on Multi-Objective Genetic Algorithm", International Journal of Computer Science Issues, Vol. 10, Issue 1, No 3, January 2013.
- [13] D. Daniel and S. J. Lovesum, "A novel approach for scheduling service request in cloud with trust monitor," in Proc. Int. Conf. Signal Process., Commun.,Comput. Netw. Technol., 2011, pp. 509–513.
- [14] Z. Wu, X. Liu, Z. Ni, D. Yuan, and Y. Yang, "A market-oriented hierarchical scheduling strategy in cloud workflow systems," The J. Supercomput., vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 256–293, 2013.
- [15] B. Saovapakhiran, G. Michailidis, and M. Devetsikiotis, "Aggregated-DAG scheduling for job flow maximization in heterogeneous cloud computing," in Proc. IEEE Global Telecommun. Conf., 2011, pp. 1–6.
- [16] M. Rahman, X. Li, and H. Palit, "Hybrid heuristic for scheduling data analytics workflow applications in hybrid cloud environment," in Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Parallel Distrib. Process. Workshops, 2011, pp. 966–974.
- [17] A. Bala and I. Chana, "A survey of various workflow scheduling algorithms in cloud environment," in Proc. Nat. Conf. Inf. Commun. Technol., 2011, pp. 26–30.
- [18] N. Kaur, T. S. Aulakh, and R. S. Cheema, "Comparison of workflow scheduling algorithms in cloud computing," Int. J. Adv. Comput. Sci. Appl., vol. 2, no. 10, pp. 81–86, 2011.
- [19] J. Li, M. Qiu, Z. Ming, G. Quan, X. Qin, and Z. Gu, "Online optimization for scheduling preemptable tasks on IaaS cloud systems," J. Parallel Distrib. Comput., vol. 72, no. 5, pp. 666–677, 2012.
- [20] J. Li, M. Qiu, J. Niu, Y. Chen, and Z. Ming, "Adaptive resource allocation for preemptable jobs in cloud systems," in Proc. Int. Conf. Intel. Syst. Design Appl., 2010, pp. 31–36.
- [21] C. Lin and S. Lu, "Scheduling scientific workflows elastically for cloud computing," in Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Cloud Comput., 2011, pp. 746–747.
- [22] S. Abrishami and M. Naghibzadeh, "Deadline-constrained workflow scheduling in software as a service cloud," ScientiaIranica, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 680–689, 2012.
- [23] Y. C. Lee, C. Wang, A. Y. Zomaya, and B. B. Zhou, "Profit driven scheduling for cloud services with data access awareness," J. Parallel Distrib. Comput., vol. 72, no. 4, pp. 591–602, 2012.
- [24] K. Kousalya and P. Balasubramanie, "Ant algorithm for grid scheduling powered by local search," Int. J. Open Problem Comput. Sci. Math., vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 222–240, 2008.

- [25] G. Ming , H. Li ,” An ImprovedAlgorithm Based on Max-Min for cloud Task Scheduling,” Tunnam University, China , (2011).
- [26] S.B.Zhan,H.Y.Huo,” Improved PSO-based Task Scheduling Algorithm in cloud computing,” In: Journal of Information and Computational Science,vol. 9,(2012),pp.3821-3829.
- [27] M.T.Aftab,M.Umer,R.Ahmad, “Job Scheduling and Worker Assignment Problem to Minimize Make span using Ant Colony Optimization Metaheuristic”,International Journal of Mechanical, aerospace, Industrial , Mechatronic and Manufacturing Engineering ,vol .6,(2012).
- [28] L. Huang , H. Chen , T. Hu ,” Survey on Resource Allocation Policy and Job scheduling Algorithms of Cloud Computing 1, “ Journal of Software, (2013), pp. 480-487.
- [29] R.G. BabuKarthik,R.Raju and P.Dhavachelvan,” Hybrid Algorithm for job scheduling:Combining the benefits of ACO and Cuckoo Search” Advancesin Computing and Information Technology. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, (2013), pp.479-490.
- [30] B.T.Bini and S.Sindhu ,” Scheduling In Cloud Based On Hyper-Heuristics ,” International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology , vol.3 , (2015), pp. 380-383.
- [31] K.M .Cho, P.W.Tsai, C.W. Tsai,” A hybrid meta-heuristic algorithm for VM scheduling with load balancing in cloud computing,” Neural Computing and Applications, (2014).